

Implementation of Principal Transformational Leadership and Independent Learning Policy in Improving Education Quality: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: The search ranges from 2015 - 2020. Most of the research results indicate that the principal transformational leadership plays an important role in shaping the quality of education in implementing independent learning education policies. First, the articles reviewed were in English, so other studies were not reviewed due to limitations in the context of several countries. Second, dissertations and theses were not discussed in this article because they could cause publication bias in the results. Third, the scope of the articles reviewed is still limited. Implementation of principal transformational leadership free learning policy in improving the quality of education can be used for various organizations in various countries.

KEYWORDS: Education Quality, Implementation, Independent Learning Policy, Principal, Transformational Leadership.

INTRODUCTION

The development of the education system in Indonesia has undergone rapid changes from time to time which encourage every principal to adapt to changes for educational transformation. Transformational leadership affects similar outcomes in culturally different countries (Malik, Javed, Hassan, & Sciences, 2017). Improving the quality of education to become superior education is still a big plan for the education authority department in Indonesia (Andriani, Kesumawati, Kristiawan, & Research, 2018). Transformational leaders win support, cooperation, and compliance with subordinates through employment, security, long-term employment, and favorable appraisals (Lee & Kuo, 2019). The principal is the person who has the highest authority in the school, because the principal is responsible for all school activities and plays an important role in improving the quality of education (Truong, Hallinger, & Sanga, 2017).

The principal as the manager of the education unit is also referred to as the education administrator and manager. The principal as manager is the key holder of the school retreat. The principal is an important factor in forming an effective school; therefore, the principal needs to have the ability, style and strategy to achieve the goals that have been set. Principal as leaders and managers of education are expected to have a leadership spirit, so that they are able and skilled to plan, organize, implement, control and control, so as to be able to disseminate, motivate and encourage the realization of the quality of teacher work. To create an environment that will foster innovation and trust, a leader needs to engage educators, stakeholders, and even students to be part of the change process. All of these are the strengths of transformational school leadership (Sun, Chen, & Zhang, 2017). There are four dimensions of transformational leadership: 1) Idealized influence, transformational leaders act as role models and display charismatic personalities that influence others to want to be more such as leaders, 2) Inspirational motivation, the ability of leaders to inspire self-confidence, motivation, and goals of followers, 3) Intellectual stimulation, the extent to which the leader provides followers with interesting and challenging tasks and encourages them to solve problems in their own way, and 4) Individual consideration, this aspect is a representation of the leader who provides support to individual needs or desires (Ihsani, 2020).

Virtue is not only related to useful values or qualities, but fundamentally forces to get something valuable (Effendi, 2020). Therefore, religious ethics is a character of faith or the virtue of faith expressed in the form of orders, norms, and virtues. The basic motivation for ethical action aims to glorify God and be useful to oneself and others. "Free Learning Education" is the concept as a response to the needs of the education system in the era of the industrial revolution (Yamin & Syahrir, 2020).

The principal is one of the components of education that has the most role in improving the quality of education (Sholikhah, 2020). A principal who truly has managerial abilities is very important, so that all resources owned by the school can be optimally

empowered to improve the quality of the institution. In connection with the quality of an institution, many factors influence its achievement. Among them are the quality of teachers, facilities and infrastructure, the quality of students and their input, and the quality of the community involved in all school activities. This low quality of schools can affect the image of the school in the eyes of the community. Efforts to improve the quality of education are continuously carried out by various parties in order to develop human resources and develop national character. Improving the quality of education is a development goal in the national education sector and is an integral part of efforts to improve the overall quality of Indonesian people (Kusumaningrum, 2019).

Based on the description above, it is necessary to find out more deeply about: How is the implementation of transformational leadership for the principal of free learning policy in improving the quality of education in the world context?

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Transformational leaders are coaches and mentors for their followers. Transformational leaders focus on the abilities and talents of each individual apart from teamwork because personal abilities are very important to achieve organizational performance (Kiran, 2020). Transformational leadership, in short, provides intellectual direction and aims to innovate within organizations, while empowering and supporting teachers as partners in making decision. Transformational leadership, the leader promotes the development of a culture that promotes better performance in the organization (Waruwu, 2020). Organizational structure is the result of many possibilities, such as strategy, culture, technology, leadership and organizational size. Transformational leaders recognize the need for change, to create and share their compelling visions with employees, guide them through adaptation, and inspire them to achieve challenging goals in institutionalizing change (Khattak, 2020).

The transformational leadership function that is carried out by the principal in leading a school can lead human resources that are led to the growing sensitivity of coaching and organizational development, development of a shared vision, distribution of leadership authority and building a mandatory school organizational culture and school restructuring schemes. The role of the principal is very important in transforming the educational process, performance, and student learning outcomes, because the quality of school leaders is related to the academic success of students; therefore, school must invest in training to upgrade the principal's leadership (Jones et al., 2015) (Tingle, Corrales, & Peters, 2019). In short, the principal plays a key role in this domain by shaping the school environment, motivating and supporting learning in school (Lijuan et al., 2016). Three types of principal leaders' profiles were identified: "principals who think about people", "principals who think administratively:" and "principals who think moderately" (Dou, Devos, & Valcke, 2017).

Educational leaders, particularly effective principals, who perform school leadership roles are a key element in effective schools. An effective leader should be able to create social change in expressing and defining transformational leaders as people who care for their followers, mobilizing their strength to fulfill their needs and potentials (Aydin, Sarier, Uysal, & practice, 2013). The principal as a leader is expected to provide leadership for teachers and for all other categories of school workers. In particular, secondary school teachers need principal leadership as the surest way to bring about the desired outcomes of educated high school graduates. Every leader tends to have a characteristic pattern or personal style that characterizes leadership, so it should be assumed that this leadership style may be related to the quality of education. Therefore, the principal in shaping the school culture needs to adopt a transformational leadership style in order to have strong, participatory, and democratic leadership. Therefore, in carrying out the school leadership function today and in the future, leadership characteristics need to be developed (Nadur, 2017).

2.1 Freedom of Learning Policy

Educational policy is defined as a collection of laws or rules governing the implementation of the education system, which includes educational goals and how to achieve these goals. As stated by Nugroho in his book entitled Education Policy, he argues that education policy is the key to excellence, even the existence of countries in global competition, so that education policy needs to get top priority in the era of globalization. Thus it can be concluded that the basis of educational policy is a legal concept that underlies the stipulation of a rule in the field of education in order to create harmony between needs and situations and conditions in the educational process. Policy is a formulation of various ways to realize the goals of national education, which are described in various educational policies (Tilaar, 2009). "Free Learning Education". This concept is a response to the needs of the education system in the era of the industrial revolution (Yamin & Syahrir, 2020).

In the era of independent learning, the demand that it be developed with independent teaching made all elements of education have to "learn independently" first. In order to be truly "Free to Learn", especially teachers, systems, and curricula must first "Learn Freedom" (Haryanto, 2020). Freedom to learn is born from the many problems that exist in education, especially those focused on the perpetrator or human empowerment. The Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia (Kemendikbud RI) emphasized a few months ago that there was a new policy in the world of education, namely "Freedom of Learning". Freedom to learn is a new policy initiated by the minister who is part of the advanced Indonesian cabinet, Nadiem Anwar Makarim. The Freedom of Learning Policy provides freedom for every educational unit to innovate. This concept must adapt to the conditions in which the teaching and learning process runs, both in terms of culture, local wisdom, socio-economics and infrastructure. A curriculum that is easy to understand and more flexible is also one of the things needed to support the implementation of Merdeka Belajar. A curriculum that can encourage teachers to choose materials or learning methods of high quality, but according to the level of competence, interests and talents of each student. On the other hand, the current Corona virus Disease (Covid-19) pandemic provides the potential for acceleration of the Freedom Learning policy. The essence of Merdeka Belajar is to explore the greatest potential of our school teachers and students to innovate and improve the quality of learning independently. Mandiri is not only following the educational bureaucratic process, but is truly educational innovation (Kemendikbud, 2020).

After the implementation of the Merdeka Belajar policy, there will be many changes, especially from the learning system. The learning system that is now only implemented in the classroom will change and be made as comfortable as possible in order to facilitate interaction between students and teachers (Zhang, Wang, Yang, & Wang, 2020). One of them is learning with an outing class, where this outing class is a learning program that aims to foster creativity so that students have certain skills and expertise. Outing class is also a fun learning method, teaching students to be closer to nature and the environment. During learning using this method, teachers and students will be more able to build intimacy, be more relaxed, and of course more enjoyable. With every day studying in the classroom for years, of course, it has become commonplace or even boring, so there is nothing wrong if we as educators provide something different to the learning process. The learning system will be designed in such a way that the character of students is formed, and is not focused on a ranking system which according to several studies is only troubling, not only for teachers but also for children and their parents (Hopman, Allegranzi, & Mehtar, 2020).

In addition, with the rankings there will also be discrimination where there is an amalgamation between the smart and the stupid. This is of course very wrong when applied in the world of education, because in essence children have their own intelligence within themselves or what is often called multiple intelligence. Multiple intelligence is defined as the capacity to solve problems and to create products in a conducive and natural environment. A good education must pay attention to the principle of independence which is the best gift given by God to humans, so that education cannot conflict with the principle of human freedom. Freedom to learn means freedom of learning, which is to give students the opportunity to learn as freely and as freely as they can to study in a calm, relaxed and happy way without stress and pressure by paying attention to their natural talents, without forcing them to study or master areas of knowledge beyond hobbies and abilities. them, so that each one has a portfolio that suits them. Because, giving burdens to students beyond their means is a sad act in common sense and cannot be done by a wise teacher (Abidah, Hidayatullaah, Simamora, Fehabutar, & Mutakinati, 2020). The potential that is owned by the smallest child must be appreciated, many children have obstacles or difficulties in learning, but if their intelligence is respected and continues to be developed, these children will become superior children in their fields. So that later a person who is competent and has a character that is embedded in him will be formed (Baro'ah, 2020).

2.2 Quality of Education

The quality of education is an important factor that must be realized in the education process (Baro'ah, 2020). The quality of education can also be called the quality of education, quality is the main problem that ensures the development of schools in achieving success in the midst of increasingly advanced competition in the world of education. The quality of education can only be realized if the educational institution has a leader who is able to manage all its resources. Therefore, in order to manage and create a quality school, it depends on the principal and teachers and other staff optimally (Awaludin, 2020). Improving quality is one of the pillars in building education, in addition to equity and expanding access and increasing effectiveness-efficiency and education governance. Improving the quality of education must receive more attention because the progress of a nation is very much dependent on the success of the nation in realizing quality education (Saleh, 2019). One of the benchmarks for improving the quality

of education is the improvement of aspects of good management. If management has been implemented properly, any institution including educational institutions will be able to produce quality performance and work (Ismail, 2020). The quality of education is one of the central issues in national education, especially in relation to the low quality of education at every level and unit of education. Efforts to improve the quality of education in this country have long been pursued (Anwar, 2018). Since Indonesia's independence until the present information era, improving the quality of education is one of the development priorities in the education sector. Various innovations and educational programs have also been pursued.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This literature review focuses on the implementation of transformational leadership for the principal of the free learning policy in improving the quality of education.

This research method of this article can be categorized as literature review research. The purpose of conducting a literature review is to obtain a theoretical basis that can support solving the problem being studied. The review process began with a search engine, Google Scholar, to search for articles with keywords: "Implementation of Transformational Leadership for the Principal of Free Learning Policy in Improving the Quality of Education". The search ranges were from 2015-2020 and identified a total of 150 studies and articles.

The criteria for inclusion in this study are as follows:

- a. Qualitative results from the implementation of the principal transformational leadership of the independent learning policy in improving the quality of education
- b. Research is carried out in the world
- c. This study uses English
- d. Dissertations and theses are excluded

The steps in the literature review of each variable of the implementation of transformational leadership for the principal of the independent learning policy school in improving the quality of education include:

Step 1: Formulate the problem

- Choose a topic that matches issues and interests
- Problems must be written completely and accurately

Step 2: Search the literature

- Find literature relevant to the research
- Get an overview of the research topic
- Sources of research resources are very helpful if they are supported by knowledge of the topic being studied.
- These sources provide an overview/summary of previous research.

Step 3: Evaluate the data

- Look at what contributions to the topic covered
- Search and find appropriate data sources as needed to support research
- Data can be in the form of quantitative data, qualitative data or data derived from a combination of the two

Step 4: Analyze and interpret

- Discuss and find and summarize the literature

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section reports the main findings from the reviewed articles and their discussion. The analysis shows that most of the articles focus on how to implement the transformational leadership of the principal of independent learning policy in education quality. The articles that have been reviewed are research conducted in a world context. Table 1 lists the results of the literature review conducted by the authors.

Table I. Implementation of Principal Transformational Leadership and Free Learning Policy in Improving Quality of Education

Author and Year	Title	Country	Method	Sample	Results
Sholikhah and Purwanta (2020)	Transformational Leadership of Inclusion Principals in SD Negeri (Public Primary School) Giwangan, Yogyakarta	Indonesia	Quantitative	-	Transformational leadership of inclusive principals in SD Negeri Giwangan is able to create change and bring about SD Negeri Giwangan achievements in the implementation of inclusive-based schools and in other fields.
Effendi, Bafadal, Sudana, and Arifin (2020)	The Principal Transformational Leadership Strategy in Developing National Policies for Strengthening Character Education in Eastern Indonesia	Indonesia	Quantitative	-	Research explains that the value of school character comes from the unification of national character the cultural values and values of Lonto Leok culture provide an effective influence about the character building of students in schools. Apart from that it explains that the application of principal-based transformational leadership role models on the approach to the dimensions of teaching culture, Lonto Leok encourages all components of the school, parents, and the community to participate actively in supporting the implementation of strengthening character education program at school.
Kiran and Kayani (2020)	Transformational Leadership as Influencing Mediating Factors Conflict Management and Performance of the Teaching Faculty at Higher Education Level: Study in Punjab, Pakistan	Pakistan	Farooqi Organizational Inventarisai Conflict	-	The relationship between conflict management and faculty performance and the mediating role of transformational leadership
Waruwu et. al (2020)	The Role of Transformational Leadership, Organizational Learning and Structure on Innovation Capacity:	Indonesia	SEM with Smart PLS 3.0 software.	645 Respondents	The results of this study are transformational leadership, organizational and organizational learning structure has a positive and significant effect on innovation capacity. Transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on

	Evidence from Indonesia Private Schools				organizational learning and organizational structure.
Khattak, Zolin, and Noor (2020).	Linking transformational leadership and continuous improvement	Australia	Quantitative	282 Employees	The results support the relationship hypothesis which suggests that trust in the leader is partial mediate the relationship of transformational leadership with organizational and continuous identification remedial efforts.
Yamin and Syahrir (2020)	Development of Free Learning Education (Study of Learning Methods)	Indonesia	Blended Learning	-	Free Learning Education is a response to the needs of the education system in the era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0. In the era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0, the main need to be achieved in the education system or more specifically in learning methods is students or learners, namely mastery of new literacy. The new literacy, namely. First, data literacy. Second, technological literacy. Finally, human literacy. In addition, the Free Learning Education system also prioritizes character education.
Truong, Hallinger and Sanga (2017)	Confucian Values and School Leadership in Vietnam: Exploring the Influence of Culture on Principal Decision Making	Vietnam	Qualitative	3 schools	In Vietnam, school leadership must adopt the values of 'indigenous perspective' to be a good leader for schools.
Baro'ah (2020)	Free Learning Policy as a Strategy to Improve the Quality of Education	Indonesia	Quantitative	-	Showed, related to the implementation of the independent learning policy aimed at improving the quality of education through the learning process, commitment from teachers, as well as creativity and support from the principal.
Kusumaningrum and Budiarti (2019)	Implementation of Transformational Leadership Style in Improving the Quality of Institutions	Indonesia	Qualitative		(1) application of a transformational leadership style in Vocational High School (SMK) Dwija Bhakti 2 Jombang; and (2) strategies to improve the quality of educational institutions through transformational leadership style at SMK Dwija Bhakti 2 Jombang.

Sri Mulani (2019)	Relationship Of Transformational Leadership Of School Principle And Teacher Discipline With The Quality Of Education Services	Indonesia	Qualitative	145 teachers	There is a positive relationship between Principal Transformational Leadership and Teacher Work Discipline with Quality Education Services at SMA East Jakarta. These findings recommend improving teacher quality services are recommended to increase the value of transformational leadership and enhance teachers work discipline so that it becomes a culture of excellence for teachers in providing good educational services
Sun, Chen and Zhang (2017)	A Review of Research Evidence on the Antecedents of Transformational Leadership	US and China	Qualitative	-	Transformational leadership is associated with three sets of antecedents, which include: (1) the qualities of the leader (eg, self-efficacy, values, traits, emotional intelligence); (2) organizational features (eg, organizational justice); and (3) co-leader characteristics (eg, follower initials level of development).
Ihsani, Inderawati, Vianty, and Machdalena (2020)	The Transformational Leadership Behavior Of School Principals Of Vocational High Schools In Palembang	Indonesia	Qualitative	-	Research shows a picture of transformational leadership demonstrate four dimensions of transformational leadership, such as idealized, inspirational influence motivation, intellectual stimulation and individual consideration. Then in this study the school was found principals carry out transformational leadership by using several ways such as building trust, motivation, facilitation and communication.
Abidah, Hidayatullaah Simamora, Fehabutar, Mutakinati, Lely (2020)	The Impact of Covid-19 to Indonesian Education and Its Relation to the Philosophy of “Merdeka Belajar”	Indonesia	Qualitative	-	Separated into four parts: "Free Learning" philosophy; physical distancing, social distancing and self-quarantine; digital studying in Indonesia to face Covid-19; 'Merdeka Learning', digital learning, Covid-19, and the author's views.
Nadur (2017).	Transformational Leadership Implementation of School Principals in Shaping School Culture in the Context of	Indonesia	Qualitative	-	1) Transformational leadership is a leadership style that emphasizes providing opportunities that improve every component of the school (namely teachers, students, school staff, parents, the community around the school, etc.) to work hard in fulfilling a good value

	Education in Indonesia				system. school residents are ready to participate and be distributed optimally to achieve the school's vision; 2) Transformational leadership is appropriate for developing school culture.
Awaludin (2020).	Principal Leadership Strategies in Developing Teacher Professional Competence to Improve Education Quality in Cendikia Muslim High School, Bogor Regency	Indonesia	Qualitative	-	Strategy and Leadership of the Principal in developing teacher professional competence to improve the quality of education that the leadership of the head of SMK Cendikia Muslim Bogor in carrying out their duties with full responsibility, to increase teacher competence and professionalism, by taking a normative approach or motivating teachers to always work according to their duties , with expertise in the field of study being taught.
Saleh (2019)	Strategy for Improving the Quality of Integrated Islamic Elementary School Education (SDIT) in East Kalimantan Province (Case study SDIT Cordova Samarinda and SDIT YABIS Bontang)	Indonesia	Quantitative	-	The teaching and learning process has the highest level of importance compared to other processes. Meanwhile, the increase in the output aspect taken is to increase academic achievement by optimizing existing components and striving to produce quality graduates and increase non-academic achievement by striving to produce students who have Islamic character and excel in the fields of arts, sports and extracurricular activities.
Malik, Umer, Javed, Muqaddas, Hassan, and Taimoor (2017).	Influence Of Transformational Leadership Components On Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment	Pakistan	Quantitative	319 employees	The TL component has a significant influence on job satisfaction along with employee organizational commitment. This investigation was carried out in only one unstable country economic and political affairs that affect the mood of individuals, it is necessary to add the question carried out in better economic conditions for an exploratory research perspective.
Lee (2019)	Principals' transformational Leadership and Teachers'work	Taiwan	Qualitative	40 schools	Primary principal transformational leadership and teacher motivation show a significant positive correlation; The transformational leadership dimensions

	Motivation: Evidence From Elementary Schools In Taiwan.				of primary school principals have predictive power for overall teacher work motivation
Anwar (2020)	The Role of the Education Quality Assurance System in Improving the Quality of Education in Madrasahs	Indonesia	Qualitative	-	The implementation of quality assurance has been carried out by optimizing the available madrasah resources. Madrasah Aliyah Negeri (MAN) Model 1 Manado (2) The impact of education quality assurance in Madrasahs can be seen in the increase in student achievement in academics, arts, and sports, thereby affirming that madrasahs have quality that is no less competitive than other schools. (3) Supporting factors for quality assurance include support for the role of the Head of Madrasah in carrying out his leadership, enthusiasm and motivation of educators and education personnel, support from the government and related Ministries, and community support. (4) Inhibiting factors for quality assurance of education in Madrasahs include limited staff, facilities, facilities and infrastructure for madrasahs, financial support and the adverse effects of technological and information developments.
Jones (2015)	Contemporary Challenges and Changes: Principals' Leadership Practices in Malaysia	Malaysia	Quantitative	7 Systems Leadership Study	Empirical evidence is emerging about principals' leadership practices and highlights some of the challenges associated with new accountability expectations and demands given to actors in Malaysia.
Dou, Devos and Valcke (2017)	The Relationships Between School Autonomy Gap, Principal Leadership, Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment	China	Quantitative	528 Teachers and 59 Principals	The significance of instructional and transformational leadership on teacher's job satisfaction and organizational commitment, mediated by the indirect impacts of the school climate and teacher's self-efficacy. The school autonomy gap, which is closely related to the leadership of the school principal, appears as important effect.

Lijuan, Hallinger and Ko (2016)	Principal Leadership and School Capacity Effects on Teacher Learning in Hong Kong.	Hong Kong	Cross-sectional and Quantitative method	32 elementary schools	The various dimensions of leadership of the principal make a significant contribution to the capacity of the school and the professional learning of teachers. The presence of cooperation, trust, communication, support for students, and alignments, coherence, and structure in schools also influence teacher professional learning.
Tingle, Corrales and Peters (2019)	Leadership Development Programs: Investing in School Principals	USA	Quantitative	59 Principals	Principals consider that training activities related to human resources, executive leadership, school culture, and strategic operations, have a “high” influence on their effectiveness as school leaders.

This section reports the main findings of the reviewed articles. The analysis shows that most of the articles focus on the Implementation of transformational leadership of the principal of free learning policy in improving the quality of education. The articles that have been reviewed are research conducted in several countries.

Based on the articles reviewed, there are various ways of collecting data related to the implementation of the transformational leadership of the principal of free learning policy in improving the quality of education. The research method used is from article to article. The most common method used is by using interviews and observations used by several authors (Ihsani, 2020; Baro'ah, 2020; Ismail, 2020; Nadur, 2017; Waruwu, 2020; Yamin & Syahrir, 2020; Sholikhah, 2020; Lee & Kuo, 2019). Research on the Implementation of Principal Transformational Leadership for Free Learning Policy in Improving the Quality of Education has been carried out in Indonesia and has been carried out in various organizations and in various countries. Table 1 shows that research has been carried out in schools, universities, and schools.

The results of the study mostly indicate that transformational leadership is a leadership style that emphasizes providing opportunities that improve each component of the school, works hard to fulfill a good value system so that every school member is ready to participate and be distributed optimally to achieve the school's vision. Free Learning Education is a response to the needs of the education system in the era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0, which shows that in relation to the implementation of the independent learning policy, it aims to improve the quality of education through the learning process, commitment from teachers, and creativity and support from school principals. Supporting factors for quality assurance include support for the role of the principal in carrying out his leadership, enthusiasm and motivation of educators and education personnel, support from the government and related ministries, and community support and factors inhibiting education quality assurance include limited personnel, facilities, facilities and infrastructure, madrasah financial support and the adverse effects of technology and information developments.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the literature review, it can be concluded that the implementation of transformational leadership for school principals and the Independent Learning Policy has a positive and significant effect in improving the quality of education in various countries including Indonesia. This shows that the implementation of transformational leadership and the Free Learning Policy will affect the improvement of the Quality of Education. This means that the implementation of the principal's transformational leadership and the Free Learning Policy plays an important role in determining the direction of development and will have a major impact on improving the quality of education.

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